

Interview Protocol - with teachers

Thank you for participating in our research. My name is Jianing Si, and I am a researcher at the University of Macau. Our study aims to understand how you perceive and address the digital safety challenges faced by children with intellectual disabilities. Throughout the interview, I will ask you a series of questions. There are no right or wrong answers; please respond based on your actual experiences. If you find any question uncomfortable, you may skip it. You can also ask questions or pause the interview at any time, and this will not affect your participation compensation.

We value your unique experiences and opinions. The interview will be recorded for research purposes, but the recording will not be made public, and your identity will remain confidential. Do you agree to the recording and to start the interview?

- What is your age?
- How long have you been working at the special education school?
- What type of children do you primarily work with? What are the specific characteristics of these children?
- What subjects and grade levels are you primarily responsible for teaching?
- Does the school provide opportunities for children to access digital resources?
- Do children have any tasks at school that require the use of mobile devices?
- Have you observed whether children have their own mobile devices? What is the ratio of ownership and usage of mobile devices?
- Do children carry mobile devices with them daily?
- What do children use mobile devices for on a daily basis?
- What settings and checks do teachers perform on students' mobile devices?
- Do you remind children to pay special attention when using mobile devices?
- Do you establish any rules in advance? What considerations are these rules based on?
- What communication techniques do you use with children? What communication methods are most acceptable to them?
- How do you teach children to distinguish the correctness of content? How do you teach them to differentiate between good and bad people? How do you teach them what is safe?
- Does the school organize courses to teach children how to use mobile devices?
- Have you personally organized teaching activities to instruct children on how to use mobile devices?
- Do you communicate with parents about their children's use of mobile devices?
- What specific content do you discuss? Is it about the constraints on the children?
- How do teachers assist or supervise children in using mobile devices? Are there any measures or management methods?
- Have children encountered any problems while using mobile devices daily?
- What risks do you think children face when independently operating mobile devices? In what usage scenarios? When using them for what purposes?
- What specific operations or information cause you concern?
- Are you worried about any specific actions children might take that could lead to problems?

- Are you concerned about the information children might encounter on mobile devices? Why?
- Do you think the degree of impact on children is intensified because they have intellectual disabilities, or is it because they are children?
- How do you think children's use of mobile devices should be restricted and regulated? For example, should daily usage time be limited? Should app downloads be restricted? Should kids mode be enabled? Are these measures effective?